

EXPERIMENTS ON THE SYNTHESSES OF FURANO COMPOUNDS. PART II

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Attempts to prepare 3-benzylcoumarones of the type (I, R = acyl) designed for a different synthesis of β -brazans have not been successful. Contrary to the observations of Gilman and his co-workers, it is shown that the cyclisation of the acid (XI) gives a mixture of the ketones (XII) and (XIII); the former has been converted into γ -hydroxy- and γ -methyl- β -brazan. Experiments on the cyclisation of the pyruvic acid of the type (XVII, R''=CH₂.CO.CO₂H) to the γ -brazan (XV, R''=CO₂H) have been so far unsuccessful. However, the hydroxy- γ -brazan (XV, R=OMe, R'=Me, R''=OH) has been synthesised according to the method of Johnson and Robertson.

In the preceding communication (*this Journal*, 1953, 30, 1) it has been shown that 2-acyl-3-benzylcoumarones may be cyclised to β -brazans. An alternative route to the β -brazans is the cyclodehydration of 3-benzylcoumarones of the type (I, R=acyl) where the acyl group is in the benzene nucleus. Synthetical experiments in this direction were therefore undertaken.

For this purpose, 2-nitro-4:5-dimethoxyphenylpyruvic acid (II) (Oxford and Raper, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 418) was converted into its oxime and then dehydrated with hot acetic anhydride to 2-nitro-4:5-dimethoxyphenylacetonitrile (III). However, attempts to prepare the ketonitrile (IV) in pure condition by condensation of the nitrile with ethyl *m*-methoxyphenoxyacetate in alcoholic sodium ethoxide, have not

been successful (cf. Avenarius and Pschorr, *Ber.*, 1929, 62, 323) due, probably to the acid hydrolysis of (IV) being rendered more facile by the substitution of the nitro group in the *ortho* position. Experiments on the synthesis of the equivalent intermediate (VIII) were next attempted. 2-Carboxy-4:5-dimethoxybenzylcyanide (VI, R=H) was conveniently prepared by the action of *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride on 2-nitroso-5:6-dimethoxy- α -hydrindone (V) (cf. Haworth and Pink, *J. Chem. Soc.*,

1926, 1368) and then methylated with diazomethane in ether to the methyl ester (VI, R=Me). The Claisen condensation of methyl *m*-methoxyphenoxyacetate with this ester in alcoholic sodium methoxide afforded, very curiously, mainly the keto-nitrile

(IX) as a result of self-condensation of the methyl ester (VI, R=Me) together with a very small quantity of the expected product (VIII). As a result of the poor yield, the project could not be pursued further. The condensation of (VI, R=Me) with methyl formate, however, gave wholly the expected *isocoumarin* (VII) (cf. Robertson *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 3378). An attempt to cyclise the keto-nitrile (IX) with sodium ethoxide to the eight-membered compound (X) was unsuccessful.

A synthesis of β -brazan successfully exploited by Mosettig and Robinson (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 61, 1150) was from γ -(2-dibenzofuryl)-*n*-butyric acid (XI) which on cyclisation with phosphoric oxide in phosphoric acid gives a mixture of ketones (XII) and (XIII) in which the former predominates. Contrary to the observations of Gilman *et al.* (*ibid.*, 1939, 61, 2842) who found (XII) as the sole product of cyclisation of (XI) with sulphuric acid, it is now found that both the ketones (XII) and (XIII) are really formed in which former is again the main product. On reaction with methylmagnesium iodide, this ketone (XII) gave 7-methyl-7:8-dihydro- β -brazan which on dehydrogenation with palladised charcoal furnished 7-methyl- β -

brazan (XIV, R=Me). Dehydrogenation of the ketone itself with palladised charcoal afforded a poor yield of 7-hydroxy- β -brazan (XIV, R=OH).

Exploratory experiments on the synthesis of γ -brazans of the type (XV, R''=H) by the cyclodehydration of appropriate 3-phenylcoumarone-2-pyruvic acid (XVII, R''=CH₂.CO.CO₂H) were carried out. 2:4-Dihydroxy-3'-methylbenzophenone (XVI, R=OH, R'=Me, R''=H) (Bhagwat and Sahane, *Chem. Abs.*, 1940, 34, 5071) was conveniently prepared by the Friedel-Crafts reaction of *m*-toluyl chloride with resorcinol in nitrobenzene (cf. Jhonson and Robertson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 2381). This was monomethylated with methyl iodide and potassium carbonate to 2-hydroxy-4-methoxy-3'-methylbenzophenone (XVI, R=OMe, R'=Me, R''=H) and then converted into 2-*m*-methylbenzoyl-5-methoxyphenoxyacetic acid (XVI, R=OMe, R'=Me, R''=CH₂CO₂H) by ethyl bromoacetate and potassium carbonate in acetone, followed by hydrolysis.

On treatment with sodium acetate and hot acetic anhydride, this phenoxyacetic acid gave 6-methoxy-3-*m*-methylphenylcoumarone (XVII, R=OMe, R'=Me, R''=H). On the Gattermann reaction with the aid of zinc chloride, this coumarone gave 2-formyl-6-methoxy-3-*m*-methylphenylcoumarone (XVII, R=OMe, R'=Me, R''=CHO) which on condensation with hippuric acid in the usual way gave the azlactone (XVIII). On alkaline hydrolysis, this compound gave a very poor yield of 6-methoxy-3-*m*-methylphenylcoumarone-2-pyruvic acid (XVII, R=OMe, R'=Me, R''=CH₂.CO.CO₂H). Attempts to cyclise this acid with glacial phosphoric acid or with hydrochloric acid in acetic acid were unsuccessful (cf. Birch and Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 503; Geissmann and Tess, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 62, 514; Horning and Koo, *ibid.*, 1951, 73, 5829).

The pyruvic acid on oxidation with alkaline hydrogen peroxide gave 6-methoxy-3-*m*-methylphenylcoumarone-2-acetic acid (XVII, R=OMe, R'=Me, R''=CH₂.CO₂H) which was prepared in quantity from the aldehyde (XVII, R=OMe, R'=Me, R''=CHO). This on oxidation with hydrogen peroxide gave 6-methoxy-3-*m*-methylphenylcoumarone-2-carboxylic acid (XVII, R=OMe, R'=Me, R''=CO₂H) which on homologation by the Arndt-Eistert procedure furnished (XVII, R=OMe, R'=Me, R''=CH₂.CO₂H) by way of the ^c amide (XVII, R=OMe, R'=Me, R''=CH₂.CONH₂). The coumarone-2-acetic acid on cyclisation according to Johnson and Robertson (*loc. cit.*), however, afforded the hydroxy- γ -brazau derivative, 6-methoxy-4'-hydroxy-7-methylnaphtho (2':1'-2:3) coumarone (XV, R=OMe, R'=Me, R''=OH).

Further experiments on the cyclisation of the keto-nitrile (IX) and analogous compounds are in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL

(Unless otherwise mentioned all m.p.s are uncorrected.)

2-Nitro-4:5-dimethoxyphenylpyruvic acid was prepared according to Oxford and Raper (*loc. cit.*) by the action of ethyl oxalate on 6-nitrohomoveratrole in the presence of potassium ethoxide in dry benzene. After the isolation of the pyruvic acid, the benzene residue on evaporation gave a mixture of unchanged 6-nitrohomoveratrole and a compound which was probably sym.-*di*-(2-nitro-4:5-dimethoxyphenyl)ethane. The latter, which is sparingly soluble in alcohol, was easily purified and obtained in small, yellow prisms, m.p. 205°. (Found: C, 55.0; H, 5.2; N, 7.0. C₁₂H₂₀O₈N₂ requires C, 55.1; H, 5.1; N, 7.1 per cent). The compound did not decolorise bromine in acetic acid.

The oxime of the above pyruvic acid was obtained by adding hydroxylamine hydrochloride (11 g.) in small portions with stirring to an ice-cold solution of the α -ketonic acid (27 g.) in sodium hydroxide (150 c.c., 8%). The purple colour of the solution disappeared. The solution was allowed to stand for 24 hours when a solid (sodium salt of the oxime) appeared. The whole was acidified and the oxime crystallised from aqueous alcohol. It was obtained in thick yellowish plates (25 g.), m.p. 168° (decomp.). (Found: N, 9.8. C₁₁H₁₃O₇N₂ requires N, 9.9 per cent).

2-Nitro-4:5-dimethoxybenzyl Cyanide (cf. Niederl and Ziering, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, **64**, 885).—The above oxime (1 part) was dehydrated by adding it carefully in small portions to warm acetic anhydride (3 parts). After the vigorous exothermic reaction was over, acetic anhydride (and acetic acid) was removed as far as possible in vacuum, and alcohol added to the residue when light yellow plates of the compound (50%) appeared. It was obtained from alcohol in nearly colorless plates, m.p. 110°. (Found: C, 54.5; H, 4.7. $C_{10}H_{10}O_4N_2$ requires C, 54.0; H, 4.5 per cent). On warming with alkali the compound gave a red solution; a deeper colour was obtained with alcoholic sodium ethoxide.

2-Carboxy-4:5-dimethoxybenzyl Cyanide.—A solution of the isonitroso compound (V, 1.4 g.) in sodium hydroxide (15 c.c., 10%) was gradually treated with constant stirring with *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride (2 g.) at the room temperature and the solution completed by warming the mixture slightly on the water-bath. The solution was cooled, filtered, acidified and the resulting solid crystallised from dilute alcohol. The product (VI, R=H) (0.64 g.) was obtained in long, colorless needles, m.p. 164-65° (cf. Haworth and Pink, *loc. cit.*, m.p. 164-65°; Robertson *et. al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 3378, m.p. 183.5°). The aqueous filtrate deposited on keeping a mixture of solids, identified as the unchanged (V) (0.14 g.) and 4:5-dimethoxyhomophthalic acid (0.2 g.) which were separated by taking advantage of the latter's solubility in acetic acid.

2-Carbomethoxy-4:5-dimethoxybenzyl Cyanide.—The above acid (VI, R=H) (3 g.) was finely powdered and suspended in dry ether (50 c.c.) and treated with an excess of ethereal diazomethane (from nitrosomethylurea, 3 g.). A vigorous evolution of nitrogen took place and the mixture was left overnight. Next day, the excess of diazomethane was decomposed with a few drops of acetic acid. The residue after removal of the ether was treated with dilute sodium carbonate solution (5%) and crystallised from methanol. The ester was obtained in colorless plates (or in prisms), m.p. 120-21°. (Found: C, 61.0; H, 5.3. $C_{12}H_{13}O_4N$ requires C, 61.3; H, 5.5 per cent).

*Experiments on the Condensation of Methyl *m*-Methoxyphenoxyacetate with 2-Carbomethoxy-4:5-dimethoxybenzyl Cyanide*.—To a solution of sodium methoxide (sodium, 0.2 g., methanol, 2.5 c.c.) was added with stirring a solution of methyl *m*-methoxyphenoxyacetate (2.0 g.) and 2-carbomethoxy-4:5-dimethoxybenzyl cyanide (1.95 g.) in dry methanol (2 c.c.). The mixture was refluxed on the water-bath for 2 hours and left overnight. Next day, the sodium salt was collected, washed with dry ether, dissolved in warm water and acidified with dilute acetic acid. The colorless solid (1.6 g.) on crystallisation from a large volume of methanol gave (IX) and obtained in beautiful colorless prisms, m.p. 263-64° (decomp.). (Found: C, 62.7; H, 5.3; N, 6.3, 6.4; OMe, 36.5. $C_{23}H_{22}O_7N_2$ requires C, 63.0; H, 5.0; N, 6.4; for 4 OMe + 1 COOMe, 35.4 per cent). The compound gives with dilute sodium hydroxide solution its sodium salt which gradually crystallises out. On treatment with ferric chloride in methanol the compound gives a faint green coloration and on keeping the solution deposits a yellow solid.

The methanolic mother-liquor after the filtration of (IX) slowly deposited a small quantity of a chalky precipitate which was purified by crystallisation from acetic acid. The compound is probably (VIII). It was obtained in nearly colorless prisms, m.p. 254° (decomp.). (Found: N, 2.9. $C_{21}H_{21}O_7N$ requires N, 3.5 per cent).

Hydrolysis of (IX).—The cyano-ketone (IX, 0.4 g.) was boiled with concentrated hydrochloric acid (60 c.c.) for 15 minutes and then further boiled with the addition of water (30 c.c.) and filtered. The filtrate deposited beautiful colorless leaflets (0.3 g.) which were collected and crystallised from boiling water (charcoal) or acetic acid. The product, which was probably the *amide* (IX, CH_2CONH_2 in place of CH_2CN), was obtained in woolly mass, m.p. 240-42°. (Found: C, 60.3; H, 5.3; N, 6.8. $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2$ requires C, 60.5; H, 5.3; N, 6.1 per cent). The compound dissolves in sodium hydroxide with a green fluorescence. With alcoholic ferric chloride the compound gives a faint green coloration and on keeping the solution deposits a yellow solid. Further hydrolysis of the amide was done by boiling under reflux with dilute sodium hydroxide till the evolution of ammonia was over. The colorless solid obtained on acidification crystallised from water in overlapping prisms (or in plates), identified as 4:5-dimethoxyhomophthalic acid, m.p. and mixed m.p. 223-24°. (Found: C, 54.6; H, 4.9. Calc. for $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_6$: C, 55.0; H, 5.0 per cent).

4-Cyano-6:7-dimethoxyisocoumarin (cf. Robertson *et. al.*, *loc. cit.*).—To dry sodium methoxide from sodium (0.46 g.) and dry methanol were added in the cold with stirring, dry ether (50 c.c.), 2-carbomethoxy-4:5-dimethoxybenzyl cyanide (1 g.) and methyl formate (10 c.c.). Reaction took place immediately and a yellowish white precipitate separated gradually. The mixture was allowed to stand overnight and the next day it was refluxed for 1 hour. The solvent was removed completely, water added, filtered and acidified with warm concentrated hydrochloric acid. The copious precipitate of the *isocoumarin* (VII) (0.9 g.) was collected and obtained from acetic acid in slender, colorless needles, m.p. 298° (corr.). (Found: C, 62.4; H, 3.9; N, 5.6. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_9\text{O}_4\text{N}$ requires C, 62.4; H, 3.9; N, 6.1 per cent). The compound may be further purified by sublimation.

Cyclisation of γ -(2-dibenzofuryl)-n-butyric Acid (cf. Robinson and Mosettig, *loc. cit.* Gilman *et. al.*, *loc. cit.*).—The acid was cyclised with sulphuric acid using Gilman's procedure. The crude product, on one crystallisation from alcohol had m.p. 127-30°. This was fractionally crystallised from benzene. The less soluble portion which contained (XII) was obtained in pure thick plates, m.p. 137° (lit., 137-38°). The oxime was obtained from alcohol in colorless prisms, m.p. 212-13° (lit., 212-13°). (Found: N, 5.5. Calc. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_2\text{N}$: N, 5.6 per cent).

The more soluble portion (m.p. ca 85°), on crystallisation from methanol, gave a mixture (m.p. ca 88-92°) consisting mica-like plates and hard prisms. These were separated mechanically and the prisms after two crystallisations from methanol gave (XIII) in a pure condition, m.p. 112-12.5° (lit., m.p. 112-13°); yield 2-3%. The oxime separated from pyridine-aqueous alcohol in colorless plates, m.p. 202.5° (lit., 202-203°). (Found: N, 5.5. Calc. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_2\text{N}$: N, 5.6 per cent).

The *2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone* crystallised from nitrobenzene-alcohol in ochreous microcrystalline powder, m.p. 319° (corr.). (Found: N, 13.3. $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_8\text{N}_4$ requires N, 13.5 per cent).

7-Methyl- β -brazan.—To a solution of methylmagnesium iodide from magnesium (0.4 g.), methyl iodide (1.5 c.c.) in ether (30 c.c.) was added with stirring at the room temperature a solution of the ketone (XII) (3 g.) in dry benzene (20 c.c.). After the initial reaction was over, the mixture was heated under reflux for 4 hours. The mixture

was then treated with ice and dilute H_2SO_4 , the ether layer separated, washed with water and concentrated, when a viscous liquid showing green fluorescence was obtained. On distillation, 7-methyl-7:8-dihydro- β -brazan (2.5 g.) was obtained at 245° - $248^\circ/35$ mm. (Found: C, 87.0; H, 6.1. $C_{17}H_{14}O$ requires C, 87.2; H, 6.0 per cent). The product (1.0 g.) was dehydrogenated with palladised charcoal (prepared according to Linstead and Thomas, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 1127) (0.1 g.) by heating in a metal-bath the temperature of which was slowly raised from 210° to 310° in course of 2 hours. The mass was extracted with benzene and the product (7-methyl- β -brazan, 0.8 g.) was obtained from benzene-alcohol in nearly colorless needles, m.p. 117° . (Found: C, 87.7; H, 5.2. $C_{17}H_{12}O$ requires C, 87.9; H, 5.2 per cent). The product may be purified by sublimation.

Although β -brazan does not give a picrate, this methyl derivative gives an unstable picrate, m.p. 126 - 27° . (Found: N, 9.2. $C_{17}H_{12}O.C_6H_3O_7N_3$ requires N, 9.1 per cent).

7-Hydroxy- β -brazan.—The ketone (XII, 0.5 g.) was intimately mixed with palladised charcoal (0.1 g.) and heated in a metal-bath at 250° - 260° for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. The crude product was extracted several times with warm sodium hydroxide (5%), filtered and the greenish solution on acidification gave 7-hydroxy- β -brazan (0.06 g.), crystallising from benzene in colorless needles, m.p. 221 - 22° . (Found: C, 82.0; H, 4.6. $C_{16}H_{10}O_2$ requires C, 82.1; H, 4.3 per cent). The compound gives a violet-red azo dye with benzenediazonium chloride.

The acetyl derivative, prepared by the action of acetic anhydride and sodium acetate on the water-bath, crystallised from acetic acid in clusters of colorless needles, m.p. 145° . This was not analysed due to shortage of the material.

2:4-Dihydroxy-3'-methylbenzophenone was prepared by the condensation of resorcinol (32 g.) and *m*-toluyl chloride (40 g.) with aluminium chloride (38 g.) in nitrobenzene (325 c.c.) during 50 hours. The complex was decomposed with ice and hydrochloric acid and after removing nitrobenzene with steam, the residual solid (52 g.) crystallised from dilute alcohol, giving the benzophenone in pale yellow prisms, m.p. 170 - 71° (lit., 168°). (Found: C, 73.4; H, 5.5. Calc. for $C_{14}H_{12}O_2$: C, 73.7; H, 5.3 per cent). With ferric chloride it gives a red-brown coloration.

The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone separated from ethyl acetate in orange-red prisms, m.p. 293° (corr.). (Found: N, 13.6. $C_{20}H_{16}O_6N_4$ requires N, 13.7 per cent).

2-Hydroxy-4-methoxy-3'-methylbenzophenone.—Methyl iodide (2.0 c.c.) was added dropwise to a solution of the above-mentioned ketone (6 g.) and potassium carbonate (10 g.) in boiling acetone (50 c.c.) during 20 minutes and the mixture heated under reflux for $1\frac{1}{2}$ hours. On isolation, the resulting crude material was boiled twice with sodium carbonate solution (2*N*) which removed the unchanged ketone. The residue was then extracted with sodium hydroxide (2×65 c.c., 5%). The alkaline solution on acidification gave the product as an oil (4.1 g.), isolated with ether. This was dried in the desiccator and employed without further purification.

The alkali-insoluble portion solidified quickly giving 2:4-dimethoxy-3'-methylbenzophenone (ca. 0.4 g.) crystallising from dilute alcohol (90%) in colorless prisms, m.p.

81-82°. (Found: C, 74.7; H, 6.1. $C_{15}H_{11}O_3$ requires C, 75.0; H, 6.2 per cent). The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone separated from ethyl acetate in beautiful orange prisms, m.p. 170°. (Found: N, 13.3. $C_{22}H_{20}O_6N_4$ requires N, 12.8 per cent).

2-m-Methylbenzoyl-5-methoxyphenoxyacetic Acid.—A mixture of the foregoing phenol (5 g.), ethyl bromoacetate (4.2 c.c.), anhydrous potassium carbonate (14 g.) and acetone (50 c.c.) was boiled under reflux for 6 hours. On isolation the resulting ethyl 5-methoxy-2-m-methylbenzoylphenoxyacetate was obtained as an oil which was hydrolysed with boiling aqueous alcoholic potash (KOH, 10g, alcohol, 50 c.c. and water, 30 c.c.) during $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. After removing alcohol in vacuum, the mixture was diluted with water (80 c.c.) and acidified. The resulting oil solidified affording the compound which separated from benzene-petroleum ether in colorless long needles, m.p. 80-81°. (Found: C, 68.1; H, 5.5. $C_{17}H_{15}O_3$ requires C, 68.0; H, 5.3 per cent).

6-Methoxy-3-m-methylphenylcoumarone.—A mixture of the above phenoxyacetic acid (2.5 g.), sodium acetate (5 g.) and acetic anhydride (20 c.c.) was heated at 160° (oil bath) for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. A brisk reaction was noted in the beginning. The product obtained by the addition of water was extracted with ether, washed with sodium bicarbonate and dried (sodium sulphate). The compound was obtained as a solid (1.8 g.), m.p. 29-30°. (Found: C, 80.2; H, 5.8. $C_{18}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 80.6; H, 5.9 per cent). The compound does not give a crystalline picrate. With sulphuric acid it gives an orange-yellow coloration.

2-Formyl-6-methoxy-3-m-methylphenylcoumarone.—A solution of the foregoing coumarone (18 g.) and anhydrous hydrogen cyanide (25 c.c.) in ether (270 c.c.) containing zinc chloride (4 g.) was saturated with dry hydrogen chloride at 0° and next day, the crystalline product washed with dry ether and hydrolysed with water (500 c.c.) on the water-bath for 45 minutes when a greenish solid was obtained. This was collected and on crystallisation from alcohol, the aldehyde was obtained in long colorless needles, m.p. 106-107°, yield 16.5 g. (Found: C, 76.2; H, 5.5. $C_{17}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 76.6; H, 5.3 per cent). The brown-red solution of this aldehyde in sulphuric acid became green (yellowish) and on dilution with water it became green and then blue.

The oxime crystallised from methanol in hard prisms, m.p. 101° (evolution of gas) with previous shrinking. (Found: C, 70.5; H, 5.4. $C_{17}H_{15}O_2N \cdot \frac{1}{2}CH_3OH$ requires C, 70.7; H, 5.7 per cent).

6-Methoxy-3-m-methylphenylcoumarone-2-pyruvic Acid.—A mixture of the above aldehyde (3 g.), hippuric acid (2 g.), sodium acetate (1 g.) and acetic anhydride (20 c.c.) was heated on the steam-bath for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour, cooled and diluted with aqueous alcohol (60 c.c., 50%). Crystallised from benzene, the resulting *azlactone* (XVIII) (3.9 g.) was obtained in small yellow needles, m.p. 205-207°. (Found: N, 3.6. $C_{26}H_{20}O_4N$ requires N, 3.4 per cent). This compound was hydrolysed with aqueous alcoholic potash (potassium hydroxide, 5 g., alcohol, 25 c.c. and water, 25 c.c.) in an oil-bath for 6 hours. In the beginning, light yellow needles appeared. After removing the tarry material by decantation, the solution was cooled, saturated with sulphur dioxide and left overnight. Next day, the mixture was filtered and the filtrate heated with concentrated hydrochloric acid on the water-bath when a yellow precipitate (0.04 g.) of the pyruvic

acid appeared. This was crystallised from ethyl acetate-petroleum ether and obtained in light yellow, tiny needles, m.p. 190° (decomp.). (Found: C, 70.0; H, 5.2. $C_{11}H_{10}O_3$ requires C, 70.4; H, 5.0 per cent). The compound gives a violet ferric chloride reaction.

6-Methoxy-3-m-methylphenylcoumarone-2-acetic Acid: Method (a).—Oxidation of the above-mentioned pyruvic acid (0.02 g.) in sodium hydroxide (5 c.c., 2%) with hydrogen peroxide (0.5 c.c., 30%) at the room temperature during 45 minutes furnished the compound which crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether in colorless needles, m.p. $132-33^{\circ}$. With sulphuric acid, the compound gave a deep yellow solution which on warming and on keeping turned green.

Method (b).—Hydrogen peroxide (5 c.c., 30%) was added dropwise to a stirred solution of the aldehyde (0.5 g.) in acetone (50 c.c.) in the presence of sodium hydroxide (10 c.c., 5%) at 40° for 1 hour. After removal of the acetone, the cooled reaction mixture was diluted with water, filtered from the gummy material and acidified giving a precipitate of the carboxylic acid (0.22 g.), crystallising from ethyl acetate-petroleum ether or from glacial acetic acid in slender, colorless needles, m.p. 190° (decomp.). This gave with sulphuric acid a deep yellow solution which on warming turned deep green. (Found: C, 72.1; H, 5.2. $C_{17}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 72.3; H, 5.0 per cent). The acid (3.8 g.) was converted into the acid chloride by means of phosphorus pentachloride (4 g.) in chloroform (80 c.c.) by warming on the steam-bath. The green solution on concentration in vacuum gave the acid chloride which solidified. A solution of the product in dry benzene (15 c.c.) was added dropwise to a solution of diazomethane (from 20 g. nitrosomethylurea) in ether (200 c.c.) at -2° . Next day, the solution was filtered from a spongy mass (polymethylene?) and the solvent removed in vacuum. The *diazoketone* crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether in yellow prisms, m.p. 99° (decomp.), yield 2.9 g. (Found: N, 9.2. $C_{18}H_{14}O_3N_2$ requires N, 9.1 per cent). A solution of the diazo-ketone in dioxane (80 c.c.) was added dropwise to a well stirred solution of silver nitrate (40 c.c., 10%) in concentrated aqueous ammonia (25 c.c.) kept at 72° . After leaving at this temperature for 1 hour, next day the mixture was filtered, poured on a large volume of cold water and the crystals collected after 4 hours. Crystallised twice from ethyl acetate-petroleum ether, the *6-methoxy-3-m-methylphenylcoumarone-2-acetamide* was obtained in colorless, slender needles (1.8 g.), m.p. $151-52^{\circ}$. (Found: N, 5.0. $C_{18}H_{17}O_3N$ requires N, 4.8 per cent). This amide (1.7 g.) was hydrolysed by boiling under reflux on the steam-bath with aqueous alcoholic potash (20 c.c., 10%) for 8 hours. After removing alcohol, the cooled residue diluted with water (75 c.c.), clarified by norite, filtered and acidified giving *6-methoxy-3-m-methylphenylcoumarone-2-acetic acid*, crystallising from benzene-petroleum ether in colorless needles, m.p. and mixed m.p. $132-33^{\circ}$, yield 1.3 g. (Found: C, 72.7; H, 5.6. $C_{18}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 72.9; H, 5.4 per cent).

6-Methoxy-4'-hydroxy-7'-methylnaphtho-(2':1'-2:3)coumarone.—Phosphoric oxide (3.5 g.) was added with stirring during 3 minutes to a warm solution of the above acid (0.6 g.) in benzene (20 c.c.). The mixture was refluxed for 3 hours, decomposed with ice and extracted with ether. The ethereal solution after washing with sodium bicarbonate was dried and evaporated leaving the *naphthocoumarone* as a pale yellow solid.

Crystallised twice from acetic acid, the compound was obtained in almost colorless needles (0.3 g.), m.p. 164-66° giving a deep red and then green coloration with sulphuric acid. (Found: C, 77.5; H, 5.0. $C_{18}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 77.7; H, 5.0 per cent).

The author wishes to thank Prof. K. Prasad, M.Sc., for the kind hospitality of his laboratory.

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Received August 9, 1952.